

The importance and calculation of threaded joints in agricultural production

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Abstract: This article presents the importance of threaded joints, their types, methods of preparation, areas of use, advantages, disadvantages, geometric parameters, and methods for testing them for strength. According to it, it is possible to select the necessary materials for the preparation of threaded joints, determine their main dimensions, and test the strength of threaded joints based on the selected material and the determined dimensions.

Keywords: threaded connection, metric, inch, fine pitch, coarse pitch, diameter, tension, strength, profile, input, parameter.

Introduction. As is known, extensive work is being carried out in agricultural production on the mechanization of agriculture. This requires the production of agricultural machinery designed to perform various types of work. It is clear that threaded joints are used in the production of agricultural machinery in most of them. Especially in agricultural machinery operating in difficult conditions, threaded joints with high strength, high rigidity, vibration resistance and the required dimensions are used [1]. It follows from this that when manufacturing threaded joints, it is necessary to study their operating conditions and, based on these studies, correctly select their material and type, based on them, theoretically substantiate the main dimensions of threaded joints with high accuracy, and at the same time test them for strength [2-3].

Research method. Machines, mechanisms, devices, devices and structures are interconnected by some units. These connections perform various functions and are primarily divided into two types: detachable and non-detachable [4].

Threaded connections are understood as the connection of parts using threads. Threads differ from each other, since they are characterized by different sizes, heights and other factors. However, many do not understand how this is regulated, and there are many other types of them, not only metric cylindrical threads [5].

Figure 1. Appearance of the thread

Their threaded parts are formed by means of bolts, screws, studs, nuts and spring washers. The main element of threaded connections is a thread.

A thread is a surface formed as a result of the helical movement of a uniform contour along a cylindrical or conical surface, in other words, a spiral with a constant pitch formed on this surface [6-7].

Depending on the shape of the surface, cylindrical and conical threads are distinguished. These two types of threads can be external and internal. In terms of the direction of rotation, the thread can be left-handed or right-handed [8-9].

Threaded joints have the following advantages:

- can work reliably enough even under very high loads;
- are easy to disassemble;
- are easy to manufacture;
- are cheaper to manufacture than other joints;
- all dimensions are standardized.

Threaded connections have the following disadvantages:

- the difficulty of the technology for manufacturing special threads;
- insufficient resistance to the effects of variable forces.

The thread can be made on the inner or outer surface of a cylinder or cone. The former is called an **internal** thread, and the latter is called an **external** thread.

If the dimensions of the thread are expressed in full, it is called a **metric** thread, and if expressed in **inches**, it is called an inch thread.

Research results and discussions. The main parameter of the thread for classification is the type of cutting profile. There are the following types of threaded connections of parts [10-11]:

1. Metric thread - one of the most common types of fastening threads. For an equilateral triangle with a profile, the angle $\alpha = 60^\circ$. The ends of the thread are made blunt, which significantly reduces the concentration of stresses, and as a result, prevents damage to the thread. The presence of a radial groove causes this type of thread to be leaky. There are types of metric threads with large and small pitches.

Figure 2. Appearance of a metric thread

The pitch of the metric thread can be 0.25 - 6 mm, the outer diameter can be from 1 mm to 600 mm. This type of threaded connection is used in the manufacture of many fasteners.

2. Inch thread - a type of thread with an equilateral triangular profile and an angle of $\alpha=55^\circ$.

Figure 3. Appearance of inch thread

The main characteristics of inch threads are as follows:

- Outer diameter - this is the longest distance between two points on the pipe. You can use a ruler, caliper, etc. to measure.
- Inner diameter - this parameter is the longest distance between the highest points of the toothed ridges. Standard measuring instruments (gauges, calipers) are also used for measurement.

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- Thread pitch - this is the distance between the side turns of the threaded connections. The height of the thread does not exceed 3 millimeters, therefore, high-precision calipers or indirect calculation methods are used for measurement.

3. Pipe thread - this type of thread is a cylindrical thread and is a small inch thread. In such threads, there is no radial groove due to the fact that the concave and convex parts of the thread are circular. It creates a hermetic joint, is used to connect pipes. The high tightness of the joint is ensured by conically prepared pipe threads.

Figure 4. View of a pipe thread

4. Trapezoidal thread is the main type of thread in screw-nut gears. The profile angle of this type of thread is an equilateral trapezoid, with an angle of $\alpha=30^\circ$. It is easier to manufacture than other connections and consumes less energy for friction. It is used to transmit reciprocating motion under load.

Figure 5. View of a trapezoidal thread.

5. Spur thread - in which the profile consists of an equilateral trapezoid with an angle of $\alpha=27^\circ$. Its useful work coefficient is higher than that of trapezoidal threads. It is used in screw-nut gears to accept high loads in one-way axial direction.

Figure 6. Appearance of the threaded rod

6. Circular thread - this is a profile consisting of arcs connected by a short straight line, the profile angle of which is $\alpha=30^\circ$. It has high dynamic strength. It is of limited use in heavy operating conditions in a polluted environment. It can be made in thin-walled parts by casting, rolling and pressing.

Figure 7. Appearance of a circular thread

There are the following methods [12-16] of thread preparation (Fig. 8.):

- thread cutting using a tap or dies. This method is used in small manufacturing enterprises. Threading is used in individual production and repair work;
- thread cutting on lathes;
- thread cutting on special thread-cutting machines;
- thread cutting by tapping on special automated thread-cutting machines. In this case, threads are prepared from most standard fasteners (for example, bolts, screws) with high productivity and low cost. The tapping threading method increases the accuracy of the part.
- melting glass, plastic, metalloceramics and similar products in parts and preparing threads from them;
- forming threads under pressure on thin walls of stamped products such as brass, plastic.

The geometric parameters of the threads are as follows [17-19]:

- d - outer diameter of the thread;
- d_1 - inner diameter;
- d_2 - average diameter of the thread;
- r - pitch of the thread (distance between the same sides of two adjacent turns in the direction of the axis);
- r_1 - pitch of the thread (distance between the same sides of one turn in the direction of the axis; in single-start threads $r=r_1$, in multi-start threads $r_1 = n \cdot r$; where: n -number of turns);
- α - profile angle of the thread.

Fig. 8. Geometrical parameters of metric threads

Fig. 9. Scheme for determining the angle of rise of the thread

$$\operatorname{tg} \psi = \frac{P_1}{\pi d_2} = \frac{np}{\pi d_2} \quad (1)$$

ψ -thread lead angle.

The calculated diameter of the thread can be expressed as follows [20-21]:

$$d_h = d - 0.94p \quad (2)$$

where, d and p are the outer diameter and pitch of the thread.

The length of the bolt, screw and stud is selected depending on the thickness of the part being joined, and other dimensions of threaded parts are taken according to the standard thread diameter [22-23].

Let's consider calculating the strength of a bolt shaft when the loads act on it differently (Figure 10) [24-26].

Figure 10. Bolted joints under different loading conditions

A tensile external force acts on the bolt shaft [27-29].

$$\sigma_{ch} = \frac{4F}{\pi d_h^2} \leq [\sigma_{ch}] \quad (3)$$

$$d_h = \sqrt{\frac{4F}{\pi[\sigma_{ch}]}} \quad (4)$$

The bolt is pulled out (picture b)

An example of such a connection is the sliding fastening of various covers that must be hermetic. In the connection, the effect of tensile stress on the bolt shaft from the tension force F and shear stress on the threads from the torque T is felt. The stress resulting from the tensile force F [30]

$$\sigma_{ch} = \frac{4F}{\pi d_h^2} \quad (5)$$

In such connections (for example, fastening the lid of a container under high pressure), hermeticity is required. The pressure acting on the container lid can be uniform or constant, and vice versa, variable.

Conclusion. According to the theoretical data on threaded joints presented above, taking into account the forces acting on threaded joints depending on the environment in which they are used, that is, the correct selection of the material of threaded joints prepared according to the stresses generated in the environment, and the correct justification of the main dimensions, will ensure that the prepared details will function for a sufficient period of time while providing sufficient strength in the environment in which they are used.

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